

Compose

Inbox

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Sent

Drafts

1

More

Labels

+

[Imap]/Drafts

The following message is being delivered on behalf of International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE).

Ahmad Juhaidi:

Thank you for submitting the manuscript, "First generation scholar in the Dayak Meratus family in Indonesia : A capital perspective" to International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE). With the online journal management system that we are using, you will be able to track its progress through the editorial process by logging in to the journal web site:

Manuscript URL:

<https://ijere.iaescore.com/index.php/IJERE/author/submission/26409>

Username: ahmadjuhaidi

If you have any questions, please contact me. Thank you for considering this journal as a venue for your work.

Dr. Lina Handayani

International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)

International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)

<http://ijere.iaescore.com>

Reply

Forward

Editor/Author Correspondence

Editor Subject: [IJERE] Editor Decision - Revisions Required

[DELETE](#)

2023-05-27 03:50 PM
The following message is being delivered on behalf of International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE).

-- Paper ID# 27448

Dear Prof/Dr/Mr/Mrs. Ahmad Juhaidi,

We have reached a decision regarding your submission entitled "Educational Capital of First Generation Scholar in Indigenous Tribe Family (The phenomenon of education in the Dayak Meratus tribe in Indonesia)" to International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE), a Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21100934092>) and Scimagojr (<https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100934092&tip=sid&clean=0>) indexed journal.

Our decision is that a re-submission is required. Please read the checklist for preparing your paper for publication at: <https://ijere.iaescore.com/index.php/IJERE/about/editorialPolicies#custom-2>. Please try to adhere to the format as closely as possible. Authors should have made substantial/intellectual contribution (the new findings with contrast to the existing works). Highlight the main theme of the work with the specific goals of the design and development approach.

Please submit your revised paper in MS Word file format, and submit revised paper within 8 weeks through our online system at same ID number (NOT as new submission) on Tab "Review" as "Author Version" file. Then, your revised paper will be judged for final decision of acceptance or rejection.

I look forward for hearing from you

Thank you

Best Regards,
Lina Handayani
Institute of Advanced Engineering and Science
ijere@iaesjournal.com

The following is an example of a template for responding to reviewers:

I would like to thank the reviewers for their insightful feedback. All comments from Reviewer 1 are highlighted in yellow, those from Reviewer 2 are highlighted in red, and those from Reviewer 3 are highlighted in green.

- Reviewer #1 -

Comment 1: There are some references that are not required.
Response: We thoroughly updated our references; 5 references were eliminated, and two were replaced by more recent publications.

Comment 2: The presentation of Figures 2 and 3 should be improved.
Response: The necessary adjustments have been made.

Comment 3: Equation (2) seems to be incorrect.
Response: Equation (2) is correct. This can be proven as follows: ...
In order to clarify equation 9 in the manuscript, the following remarks have been added...
etc.

All changes for reviewer 1 are highlighted in yellow in the main text.

- Reviewer #2 -

Comment 1:
Response:

Comment 2:
Response:

Comment 3:
Response:

All changes for reviewer 2 are highlighted in red in the main text.

Etc.

Such a document clarifies everything and will aid the reviewers in evaluating the work fast.
When providing your amended primary document files, you must also upload your corrections statement. Before your manuscript, the declaration of revisions should appear.

Reviewer C:

The IJERE form to evaluate submitted papers

Content:
Good

Significance:
Good

Originality:
Very good

Relevance:
Good

Presentation:
Fair

Recommendation:
Fair

Comments to the Author

This comment will be visible to the Author

:

The content need to be restructure by adding sub heading. There are few paragraphs in the literature review that not synchronize with the content. The authors can explain each of the capital in different sub heading to create understanding. Citation also need to be proofread as there are few not in the format. The quote by informants format also not consistent, few in the paragraph and few in its on paragraph. More figure can be used to show more on the findings.

Reviewer D:

The IJERE form to evaluate submitted papers

Content:
Very good

Significance:
Good

Originality:
Fair

Relevance:
Very good

Presentation:
Good

Recommendation:
Good

Comments to the Author

This comment will be visible to the Author

:

Minimize thesis numbering style.
Abide to the journal format.
Minor grammar check needed

International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)
<http://ijere.iaescore.com>

Author Subject: Educational Capital of First Generation Scholar in Indigenous Tribe Family [DELETE](#)
(The phenomenon of education in the Dayak Meratus tribe in Indonesia)

2023-
06-04
01:14
PM

The following message is being delivered on behalf of International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE).

Dear Editor

I would like to thank the reviewers for their insightful feedback. All comments from Reviewer C are highlighted in blue and those from Reviewer D are highlighted in yellow.

REVIEWER#C

Comment 1: The content need to be restructure by adding subheading.
Response :The necessary subheading has been made.

Comment 2: There are few paragraphs in the literature review that not synchronize with the content.

Response : The necessary adjustments have been made.

Comment 3: The authors can explain each of the capital in the different subheading to create understanding.

Response : The necessary subheading has been made.

Comment 4: Citation also need to be proofread as there are few not in the format.

Response : The necessary adjustments have been made

Comment 5: The quote by informants format also not consistent, few in the paragraph and a a few in its on paragraph.

Response : The necessary adjustments have been made

Comment 6: More figure can be used to show more on the findings.

Response : The necessary figure have been added : Figure 2 and 3

All changes for reviewer C are highlighted in blue in the main text

REVIEWER#D

Comment 1 : Minimize thesis numbering style.

Response : The necessary subheading has been made.

Comment 2: Abide to the journal format.

Response : The necessary adjustments have been made

Comment 3: Minor grammar check needed

The necessary adjustments have been made

All changes for reviewer D are highlighted in yellow in the main text.

International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)
<http://ijere.iaescore.com>

Editor Subject: [IJERE] Editor Decision [DELETE](#)

2023-06-30 01:55 PM The following message is being delivered on behalf of International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE).

-
- Ref. from Journal article must be completed with vol., issue, pages, DOI
 - Update references in recent 5 years
 - mention each table/figure explicitly and correctly before it appears

International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)
<http://ijere.iaescore.com>

Author Subject: Educational Capital of First Generation Scholar in Indigenous Tribe Family [DELETE](#)
(The phenomenon of education in the Dayak Meratus tribe in Indonesia)

2023-07-10 03:13 AM The following message is being delivered on behalf of International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE).

I want to thank the editor for the feedback.

Editor Comment #1: Ref. from Journal article must be completed with vol., issue, pages, DOI

Response: The necessary elements have been completed. However, not all journals have "volume" and "number /issue", such as references (1). (45)

Editor Comment #2: Update references in recent 5 years

Response: The references have been updated

Editor Comment #3: mention each table/figure explicitly and correctly before it appears

Response: The necessary revisions have been made.

Looking forward to hearing good news from you

International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)
<http://ijere.iaescore.com>

Editor Subject: [IJERE] Editor Decision [DELETE](#)

2023-07-10 04:34 AM The following message is being delivered on behalf of International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE).

-
- some figures are unclear/blur.
 - - Write the decimal in English, mind all tables/figures

International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)
<http://ijere.iaescore.com>

Author Subject: Educational Capital of First Generation Scholar in Indigenous Tribe Family [DELETE](#)
(The phenomenon of education in the Dayak Meratus tribe in Indonesia)

2023-07-10

02:04 PM The following message is being delivered on behalf of International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE).

Dear Editor

With reference to your email, we have recently sent you our revised manuscript. Please find attached our manuscript.

We look forward to hearing from you.

Best regards

Ahmad Juhaidi

International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)
<http://ijere.iaescore.com>

Editor Subject: [IJERE] Editor Decision [DELETE](#)

2023-07-12 08:52 AM The following message is being delivered on behalf of International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE).

-- Paper ID#
-- Authors must strictly follow the guidelines for authors at
<http://iaescore.com/gfa/ijere.docx>
-- Number of minimum references is 30 sources (mainly journal articles) for research paper
-- and minimum 50 sources (mainly journal articles) for review paper

Dear Prof/Dr/Mr/Mrs: Ahmad Juhaidi,

It is my great pleasure to inform you that your paper entitled "Educational Capital of First Generation Scholar in Indigenous Tribe Family (The phenomenon of education in the Dayak Meratus tribe in Indonesia)" is conditionally ACCEPTED and will be published on the International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE), a SCOPUS (<https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21100934092>, SJR: 0.308 (SJR Q3), CiteScore: 1.3 and SNIP: 0.582) and ERIC (<https://bit.ly/2EI8hDj>) indexed journal. Congratulations!

Please prepare your final camera-ready paper (in MS Word or LATEX file format) adheres to every detail of the guide of authors (MS Word: <http://iaescore.com/gfa/ijere.docx>, or <http://iaescore.com/gfa/ijere.rar> for LATEX file format), and check it for spelling/grammatical mistakes. Then you should upload your final paper to our online system (as "author version" under our decision, NOT as new submission).

You should submit your camera-ready paper (along similarity report by iThenticate/Turnitin that less than 20%, and with your payment receipt) within 6 weeks.

I look forward to hearing from you.

Thank you

Best Regards,
Dr. Lina Handayani

URGENT!! Pay attention to the following instructions carefully! YOU MUST DO!!

- 1). PLEASE ADHERE STRICTLY THE GUIDE OF AUTHORS
<http://iaescore.com/gfa/ijere.docx> (Use this file as your paper template!!) and pay attention to the checklist for preparing your FINAL paper for publication:
<http://ijere.iaescore.com/index.php/IJERE/about/editorialPolicies#custom-2>
- 2). It is mandatory to present your final paper according to "IMRADC style" format, i.e.:
 1. INTRODUCTION
 2. The Proposed Method/Framework/Procedure specifically designed (optional)
 3. METHOD
 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION
 5. CONCLUSIONSee <http://iaescore.com/gfa/ijere.docx>
- 3). Add biographies of authors as our template (include links to the 4 authors' profiles, do not delete any icons in the template).
--> Provide links for all authors to the 4 icons (Scholar, Scopus, Publons and ORCID). It is mandatory!! See <http://iaescore.com/gfa/ijere.docx>
- 4). Use different PATTERNS for presenting different results in your figures/graphics (instead of different colors). It is mandatory!! See <http://iaescore.com/gfa/ijere.docx>
- 5). Please ensure that all references have been cited in your text. Use a tool such as EndNote, Mendeley, or Zotero for reference management and formatting, and choose IEEE style. Each citation should be written in the order of appearance in the text in square brackets. For example, the first citation [1], the second citation [2], and the third and fourth citations [3], [4]. When citing multiple sources at once, the preferred method is to list each number separately, in its own brackets, using a comma or dash between numbers, as such: [1], [3], [5]. It is not necessary to mention an author's name, pages

used, or date of publication in the in-text citation. Instead, refer to the source with a number in a square bracket, e.g. [9], that will then correspond to the full citation in your reference list. Examples of in-text citations:

This theory was first put forward in 1970 [9].

Zadeh [10] has argued that ...

Several recent studies [7], [9], [11]-[15] have suggested that....

... end of the line for my research [16].

6). Please present all references as complete as possible and use IEEE style (include information of DOIs, volume, number, pages, etc). If it is available, DOI information is mandatory!! See <http://iaescore.com/gfa/ijere.docx>

In order to cover part of the publication cost, each accepted paper is charged: USD 335. This charge is for the first 8 pages, and if any published manuscript over 8 pages will incur extra charges USD50 per page. For Indonesian authors, please refer to xe.com for the USD to IDR currency conversion.

The payment should be made by bank transfer (T/T):

Bank Account name (please be exact)/Beneficiary: LINA HANDAYANI
Bank Name: CIMB NIAGA Bank
Branch Office: Kusumanegara Yogyakarta
City: Yogyakarta
Country : Indonesia
Bank Account #: 760164155700
SWIFT Code: BNIAIDJAXXX

or as alternative, you can pay by using PayPal to email: info@iaesjournal.com

IMPORTANT!!!

- You should submit your payment receipt (along with your camera-ready paper and similarity report by iThenticate/Turnitin that less than 20%) within 6 weeks to email: ijere@iaesjournal.com

- All correspondence should be addressed to the emails (support by phone is not provided).

- Due to the high demand for publication and many papers in the queue, the schedule of publication is in about 9 -12 months after the acceptance notification is issued. Certificate of Acceptance can be requested by contacting septian@iaescore.com cc ijere@iaesjournal.com

International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)
<http://ijere.iaescore.com>

Author Subject: Educational Capital of First Generation Scholar in Indigenous Tribe Family [DELETE](#)
(The phenomenon of education in the Dayak Meratus tribe in Indonesia)

2023-07-13 02:37 AM The following message is being delivered on behalf of International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE).

Dear Editor

Thank you for your email about IJERE Acceptance. We are very happy to hear from you. With reference to your email, please find attached the final version of the manuscript.

We are looking forward to the good news from you.

Best regards
Ahmad Juhaidi

International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)
<http://ijere.iaescore.com>

Close

International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)

CERTIFICATE OF ACCEPTANCE

The manuscript (IJERE- 27448) entitled:

Educational capital of first generation scholar in indigenous tribe family (The phenomenon of education in the Dayak Meratus tribe in Indonesia)

Authored by:

Ahmad Juhaidi, Analisa Fitria, Noor Hidayati, Ridha Fadillah

The manuscript has been accepted in IJERE (ISSN 2252-8822)

<https://ijere.iaescore.com>

October 20, 2023

Prof. Dr. Yeo Kee Jiar
Editor-in-Chief